

Analysis of Spatio-temporal Changes of Urban Land Use Using Remote Sensing and GIS: A Case Study of Bhubaneswar City, Odisha

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Abstract

Remote sensing and GIS technology are very useful in mapping of natural resources and urban studies. Urbanization being a dynamic force, its impact is seen in both spatial and temporal variation of urban land use. Most of the urban areas are increased due to urbanization and thereby creating urban sprawl. Bhubaneswar is the capital of the state of Odisha, between 20° 12' N and 20° 23' N latitudes and 85° 44' E and 85° 54' E longitudes. Land use /land cover maps were prepared by using satellite data of IRS-1D PAN (2000), Cartosat-1 (2005) and IRS-P6 LISS-IV (2010) and ground checks during field survey. The changes in urban land use pattern over a period of time were studied using multirate and multisensor (2000-2010) remote sensing data. The main aim of this study is to analyze the spatio-temporal changes of land use in the city as well as mapping urban sprawl. Based on the urban land use /land cover analysis, spatial growth of urban centers and the population have been projected for the different periods.

Key words: Remote Sensing, Geographic Information System, Land Use, Urban sprawl

Introduction

Industrialization and technology development had brought rapid urbanization in India. Numerous social, cultural, economic and political incentives have encouraged urban expansion as well as population growth. With the increased urban population, most of the land use changes have been dramatic. Changes have occurred in relation to the location of urban centers as well as to the spatial extent of land dedicated to urban uses. Bhubaneswar is also one of the fast growing cities in Odisha State and facing with urbanization problems. The urbanization process and population growth are directly proportional in various growing cities. With the urbanization going on at a very fast pace, demand for land is very strong in Bhubaneswar. The land use/land cover change of a region is an outcome of natural and socio-economic factors and their utilization by man in time and space. Land is becoming a scarce resource due to immense agricultural and demographic pressure. Hence, information on LU/LC and possibilities for their optimal use is essential for the selection, planning and implementation of land use schemes to meet the increasing demands for basic human needs and welfare. This information also assists in monitoring the dynamics of land use resulting out of changing demands of increasing population. LU/LC change has become a central component in current strategies for managing natural resources and monitoring environmental changes.

Remote sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) are now providing new tools for advanced ecosystem management. Remote Sensing data will be used for mapping of land use/ land cover, monitoring and updating while GIS will be applied to a wide range of operating a spatial and non-spatial data.

A number of works has been carried out in urban and regional planning and related studies by using aerial photographs and remote sensing since 1966. Sokhi, *et. al.* (1987) had carried out a study on the topic of "Satellite remote sensing in urban sprawl mapping and monitoring- A case study of Delhi", with an objective to prepare a land use classifications system. Land use map of TM FCC on 1:50,000 and monitoring of urban sprawl of Delhi on 1:50,000 scale by using the satellite data of LANDSAT_ MSS are considered for various years. Ramesh and Sharma (1989) had carried out a case study as topic of Urban sprawl mapping and monitoring of Jaipur region. Main objective of the study was to monitor urban sprawl of Jaipur city and its environment using multirate sensors. Marcus and Baburu (1992) have carried out a

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case study at Saharanpur city, under the topic of identification of potential areas for future residential development remotely sensed data products like TM cover large and give synoptic view. This can be used as working base map and for updating. Sastry and Pathan (1993) have carried out urban growth trend analysis using GIS, a case study of Bombay Metropolitan region. In this case study, the objective was to analyze the physical growth of urban areas using multi-date remote sensing data and to identify the areas suitable for urban development. Mohanty and Mishra (1995) have done a site suitability analysis for urban development of Bhubaneswar city. For this study they had utilized remote sensing data, particularly large scale aerial photographs to generate spatial information database. In 2009, Urban Land Use Change Analysis and Modeling: a case study of Setubal and Sesimbra, Portugal was written by Araya (2009). In this study, the urban land use change analysis and modeling was based on three LULC maps: Landsat (1990), LISS-III (2000) and SPOT (spring) (2006) with different MMU, and various ancillary data. In 2005, Urban Land Cover/Land Use Change Detection in National Capital Region (NCR) Delhi: a study of Faridabad District was carried out by Madan Mohan (2005) in India. In this study the IRS-1C, IRS-1D PAN and LISS-III data were used. Land use/land cover map prepared from these satellite data and analysed the urban land cover and existing land use changes. According to the study, remote sensing and GIS are very useful for urban planning, monitoring, updating and change detection, and mapping.

Aim

To analyse the spatio-temporal changes of urban land use of Bhubaneswar City and its surroundings using multirate Remote Sensing data.

Objectives

- To prepare the land use/ land cover maps of Bhubaneswar City from Remote-Sensing data
- To examine the changes in Land use/land cover distribution during 2000-2010
- To project the population and urban area growth.

Location of Study Area- Bhubaneswar City

History of Bhubaneswar City: Odisha was constituted as a separate province in the year 1936 with its capital at Cuttack. Subsequently it was, however, felt that Cuttack could not continue to be the capital of the state on account of certain physical constraints like lack of sufficient space for horizontal expansion, liabilities to flooding, seepage of water through Mahanadi and Kath Jodi embankment, high subsoil water level, inherent difficulties in providing efficient drainage and sewerage facilities. The selection of site for new capital of the state was one of the major development proposals of the committee on reconstruction planning. On 13th April 1948, Bhubaneswar was declared as the capital of Odisha designed by the German Architect Dr. Otto H. Koeingsberger. The first named, Orissa was renamed as Odisha on November, 9, 2010. Bhubaneswar has been a place of religious and cultural efflorescence through the ages and today the city reflects a unique harmony between antiquity and urbanity.

Physical Background of Study Area: Bhubaneswar is located in the Khurda District of the state Odisha between 20°12'N to 20°23'N latitudes and 85°44'E to 85°54'E longitudes on the western fringe of the coastal plain across the main axis of the Eastern Ghats. It is situated on the Howrah- Chennai main south eastern Railway line at 435 km from Howrah and 1215 km from Chennai and the National Highway No.5 connecting Kolkata and Chennai passes through the city. The river Daya which has branched off from Kuakhai flows along the south eastern part of the city. Topographically Bhubaneswar forms an undulating hilly terrain with an average elevation of 45 meters above the mean sea level. It can be divided into two major parts

namely western upland and eastern lowland. Soil of Bhubaneswar is mostly hard red lateritic soil in the north and western part. The eastern and southern part consists of alluvial soil which is very good for agricultural activity. It enjoys a humid tropical climate. The vegetation of Bhubaneswar city and its surroundings are broadly classified as tropical moist deciduous (mixed type). According to the Census 2001, the Population of the Bhubaneswar is approximately 658,220.

Figure 1. Location of Bhubaneswar City

Data base and Methodology

The present study is based on the temporal remote sensing spatial data as well as non-spatial data available from the various sources. Indian Remote Sensing Satellite IRS-1D PAN with spatial resolution of 5.8 m year (2000), Cartosat-1 (IRS-P5) with 2.5 m year (2005) and Resourcesat-1 (IRS-P6) LISS-IV year (2010) with 5.8 m images had been used in this study. IRS-1D PAN data was geometrically corrected using Ground control points (GCP's). And then Registration of Cartosat-1 and LISS IV data was done using IRS-1D PAN from Erdas software. Survey of India (SOI) topo sheets on the scale of 1:50,000 have also been used for the study.

Vector data of LU/LC classification was prepared by visual interpretation method had based on tone, shape, texture and pattern as well as associated elements from these three sensors data of 2000, 2005 and 2010. Ground checked was carried out for doubtful areas and accordingly find LU/LC maps prepared for the temporal satellite data. Spatio-temporal changes of land use were detected through GIS overlay analysis with Arc-GIS software. Geographic Information System (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) tools have been used to find out the land use / land cover changes during 2000-2010 period in Bhubaneswar city. Furthermore, ancillary data such as existing land cover maps and Google map were integrated in the study. Population data for the census years of 1921-2001 was also used to predict population growth for future and analyze the pattern of urban sprawl or growth. Two methods of data analysis were adopted in this study. (i) Calculation of the area (in hectares) of the resulting land use/ land cover type for each study year and subsequently comparing the results. (ii) Overlay operations, it identifies the actual location and magnitude of changes. Boolean logic was applied to the result through Arc-GIS software which assisted in mapping out separately areas of change for which magnitude was later calculated.

Analysis

The rapid urbanization, increased population, industrial development as well as economic development caused great changes in urban area. These changes more or less affected surrounding of urban areas. Especially, a lot of forest, agricultural land, open space, and ecologically sensitive habitats etc. are lost for urban expansion and development. As population increases in an area, a city expands to accommodate the growth; this expansion is considered as sprawl. Usually sprawls take place on the urban fringe, at the edge of an urban area or along the highways.

Increasing urbanization and industrialization is resulting in accelerating the growth of existing urban centers and causing faster rate of spatial sprawl. In particular, urbanization in developing countries has produced large concentrations of urban squatters / slums and irregular developments which are in the marginal locations and hazardous areas, exposed to periodic and seasonal flooding, prone to health hazards and other related problems. Bhubaneswar city is also experiencing similar problems because the sites with their inherent physical short comings (low lying areas and river bank etc.) have been urbanized. And then, urban sprawl is haphazard development along major transportation network and along ten streams running east to west from the city.

Bhubaneswar is one of the fast growing cities in India. But the growth of Bhubaneswar is restricted by the presence of the reserve forest in the northwestern part and the flood plains in the eastern part. The city initially evolved in rectangular shape on a grid iron pattern outward from the main transport routes. The road structure of the city is also expanding as per development plan. Urban sprawl in the city is consuming peripheral lands resulting in large scale land use change. Planners have no up to date information about changing land use pattern which is very much useful in proper planning and management.

Land Use /Land Cover Classification and Distribution: In this study, a detailed classification system has being adopted for mapping by using high resolution satellite data. There are different classification schemes that are being adopted for urban LU/LC system. Details of each class are described as Residential urban, Residential other, Commercial, Industrial, Public/Semipublic/Institution, Recreational, Agricultural land, Forest land, Public utility, Transportation, Waste land, Vacant land under development, Vacant land within developed area, Water bodies/ wet land and Others.

The land use/ land cover distributions for each study year as derived from the satellite data are presented in the following figures and tables.

In 2000, agricultural land and forest land occupy 8784 ha and 4778.24 ha, respectively. The agricultural land is the largest land use of the city. Vegetation is also more than half of the agricultural land. The total residential area is 4963.77 ha and institutional area is 1022.8 ha. The total vacant land is 3497.5 ha. Waste land area, water bodies and others are 1150.13 ha, 1369.57 ha and 696.43 ha. Public utility is a little and commercial is 271.69 ha.

In 2005, agricultural land is 8421.87 ha and forest land is 4274.5 ha. The total residential area is 6131.72 ha and institutional area is 1218.77 ha. The total vacant land is 3547.81 ha. Waste land area, water bodies and others are 824.85 ha, 1361.12 ha and 447.58 ha. Public utility land use increasing is a little. Commercial occupies 272.03 ha.

In 2010, agricultural land is 6827.15 ha and forest land is 3343 ha. The total residential area is 7568.8 ha and institutional area is 1347.16 ha. The total vacant land is 4714.04 ha. Waste land area, water bodies and others occupy 365 ha, 1371.86 ha and 464.13 ha respectively. Public utility occupies 39.15 ha and commercial is 320.92 ha.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Figure 2, 3, 4. Land use/ land cover maps of Bhubaneswar City (2000, 2005, 2010)
 Source: IRS-1D PAN, 16 February, 2000, Cartosat -1(IRS-P5), 15 November, 2005, Resourcesat-1(IRS-P6) LISS-IV, 29January, 2010

Table 1. LU /LC Distribution of Bhubaneswar City (2000-2010)

LU/LC	2000		2005		2010	
	AREA (ha)	AREA %	AREA (ha)	AREA %	AREA (ha)	AREA %
Residential _ Urban	2586.93	9.31	3481.57	12.54	4303.15	15.50
Residential_ Other	2376.84	8.56	2650.15	9.54	3265.65	11.76
Commercial	271.69	0.98	272.03	0.98	320.92	1.16
Industrial	357.75	1.29	376.58	1.36	481.37	1.73
Public/semipublic/institution	1022.80	3.68	1218.77	4.39	1347.16	4.85
Recreational	556.61	2.00	560.24	2.02	580.00	2.09
Agricultural land	8784	31.63	8421.87	30.33	6827.15	24.59
Forest	4778.24	17.21	4274.50	15.39	3343	12.04
Public utility	35.26	0.13	35.95	0.13	39.15	0.14
Transportation	283.43	1.02	294.26	1.06	344.70	1.24
Wasteland	1150.13	4.14	824.85	2.97	365.00	1.31
Vacant land under development	2607.81	9.39	2668.49	9.61	3853.65	13.87
Vacant land within developed area	889.79	3.20	879.32	3.17	860.39	3.10
Water bodies/wet land	1369.57	4.93	1361.12	4.90	1371.86	4.94
Others	696.43	2.50	447.58	1.61	464.13	1.67
Total	27767.28	100	27767.28	100	27767.28	100

Source: Calculated from Land Use/Land Cover Map (2000-2010)

Land use /Land cover Changes (2000-2010):

Figure 5. Land Use/Land Cover Changes (2000-2005)

Source: Based on Fig. 2 and 3

Figure 6. Land Use/Land Cover Changes (2005- 2010)

Source: Based on Fig. 3and 4

Figure 7. Land Use / Land Cover Statistics of Bhubaneswar (2000-2010)

Source: Based on Land Use/Land Cover Map (2000-2010)

During 2000-2010, it was observed that majority of the changes occurred from agriculture and forest. Residential areas are changed from 17.87% in 2000 to 27.26% in 2010. Agricultural area decreased 5.17% during 2000-2010. Forest area also decreased. Most of the agricultural areas, forest area and vacant land were changed as residential areas as well as other categories with the high rate during 2000-2010. The changing of agriculture to vacant land is also increased. According to Table 1, agricultural areas and forest land had 31.63% and 17.21% of all land use type. It has decreased to 30.33% and 15.39% in 2005 and 24.59% and 12.04% in 2010. Because of the increasing population and residential areas expansion occurred on agricultural areas and forest area. Most people in rural area abandoned their agricultural land and migrated to urban area because of low per capital income in agricultural sector and good employment opportunities in urban area. Also, waste lands decreased from 4.14% to 1.31% during the 2000-2010. Vacant land under development area increased from 9.39% to 13.87% during 2000-2010. Most of the vacant lands are converted to residential areas, institution as well as industrial areas. According to Figure 7, agricultural land and forest area suddenly decreased and residential area and vacant land under development area increased during 2000-2010.

Urban Area Expansion (Urban Sprawl) during 1930-2010: Urban sprawl analysis has been carried out using satellite data, topo sheets and ancillary data for the periods 1930 to 2010.

Figure 8. Urban Sprawl of Bhubaneswar City (1930-2010)

Source: Topo sheets and Satellite Data

Table 2. Population growth of city based on (1921-2001) census

Year	Population	Growth (%)	Density
1921	8170	-	0.29
1931	9024	10.4	0.32
1941	9253	2.5	0.33
1951	16512	78.4	0.59
1961	38211	131.4	1.38
1971	105514	176	3.80
1981	219211	107.8	7.89
1991	411542	87.5	14.82
2001	658220	60.0	23.70

Source: Census of India

Based on urban sprawl map, the built up area of the Bhubaneswar was 104.89 ha in 1930. In 1956, the built- up area increased to 1654.9 ha because it became the capital city of the Odisha after 1948, as most of the people migrated from rural area to urban area because of the employment opportunity, economic development, and good transportation, etc. During 1930-2010, urban area expansion continuously increased from 104.9 ha to 14008 ha due to the population increased.

Projection of Population and Urban Area Growth

Population Growth: According to the population census (1921-2001), the city had a population of 8170 in 1921. Later, it had abruptly increased to the population of 38211 with the growth rate of 131.4% during the period 1951-1961 because of the shifting of the capital city of the State from Cuttack to Bhubaneswar. The city continued to grow the population of 105514 with population growth 176% during 1961-1971. Due to the opportunities of job, administrative city, growth in tertiary sector which caused the natural growth and migration as well, population growth increased. Table 2 shows the population growth of city since 1921 to 2001.

Projection of Population Growth and Urban Growth: Population projection was carried out for year 2021 taking census of 1921-2001 as input. According to the exponential trend line $Y = 8E-49e^{0.062x}$, $R^2 = 0.954$, Bhubaneswar population will be estimated to be 2150000 for year 2021.

Figure 9. Population Growth of Bhubaneswar City (1921-2001)
Source: Based on Census of India

Table 3. Population Projection of Bhubaneswar City (1921-2021)

Year	Population	Density
1930	8935	0.32
1956	22056	0.79
1968	68746	2.47
1974	143114	5.15
1981	219211	7.89
1985	293546	10.50
1990	390000	14.04
1997	550000	19.80
2000	630000	22.68
2005	810000	29.10
2010	1100000	39.61
2021	2150000	77.42

Source: Calculated from Fig. 9 equation

Urban Area Growth: According to the exponential trend line of urban area $Y = 4E-42e^{0.052x}$, $R^2 = 0.904$, the requirement of urban area for year 2021 was estimated to be 25008 ha for 2021.

Figure 10. Urban Area Expansion of Bhubaneswar City (1930-2010)
Source: Based on Table 4

Table 4. Urban Area Expansion of Bhubaneswar City (1930-2010)

Year	Urban Area (ha)	Growth (%)
1930	104.9	-
1956	1654.9	1478
1968	2237.9	35
1974	3234.2	45
1981	4077.7	26
1985	5091.8	25
1990	5767.1	13
1997	5958	3.31
2000	6524	9.4
2005	8052	23.4
2010	14008	74

Source: Topo sheets and Satellite Data

During 1930-1956 the construction of city was started and during 1930-56 many urban facilities were provided apart from large scale construction of residential quarters, so that the population growth might be four times less the urban area growth. There is a total absence of provision of areas for a number of urban activities such as industrial, institutional, etc. which were not envisaged. During 1956-68 the population growth rate was four times of the area growth, as during this period employees of various departments came to reside in residential quarters, construction for the government employees. During 1968-74 the population growth and urban area growth were proportional. During 1974-81 the population growth rate doubled compared to urban area growth. From 1981 to 1985 data, even though, the population growth is proportional to urban area growth. During 1985-1990, the growth rate of population was also

decreasing. From 2000 to 2010 showed tremendous rise in the built up area from agricultural area, forest and open spaces. Urban area increased by 1528 ha during 2005-2010 and 5956 ha during 2005-2010. According to projection of population growth and urban growth area, it was estimated for year 2021. This correlation of population growth and urban area has been directly proportional. In Bhubaneswar, the urban land use of the city over a period of 1930-2010 increased 13903.1 ha. In this period, industrial and residential areas were dominantly expanded. The land use/land cover maps were prepared for the year 2000, 2005 and 2010. Then, these maps were overlaid to find the land use/land cover changes between 2000- 2005 and between 2005- 2010. After overlaid these maps, the amount of land use change from agricultural and forest to other land uses was found. Major increase in land use categories was observed in residential area, vacant land, institution and industrial area which accounted to 1458.9 ha during 2000-2005 and 3004.61 ha during 2005-2010.

Figure.11 Relationship between Population and Urban Growth

Source: Based on Table 5

Table 5. Projection of Population Growth and Urban Growth (1930-2021)

Year	Urban Area (ha)	Growth (%)	Population	Growth (%)
1930	104.9	-	8935	-
1956	1654.9	1478	22056	146.85
1968	2237.9	35	68746	211.69
1974	3234.2	45	143114	108.17
1981	4077.7	26	219211	53.17
1985	5091.8	25	293546	33.91
1990	5767.1	13	390000	32.86
1997	5958	3.31	550000	41.03
2000	6524	9.4	630000	14.54
2005	8052	23.4	810000	28.57
2010	14008	74	1100000	35.8
2021	25008	78.5	2150000	95.45

Source: Based on Fig. 9 and 10

In this study, unplanned residential development is more than planned residential development. Unplanned development is more on agricultural land and forest area. New urban development mainly occurs on agriculture and forest land.

Findings and Conclusion

The urban LU /LC have been dynamic in nature over a period in Bhubaneswar city. There are number of implications of urbanization on the land use / land cover changes as the landscape’s physiological destruction, illegal land encroachment and shrinkage of vegetation cover etc. Due to rapid increase in population, the land values have gone high in and around the Bhubaneswar City. The city’s urban centers must grow in harmony to share the population pressure on the city. So, it is expected that during the urban development process the agricultural land converted into the built-up land result to increase in land value which can be used for financing of the urban development. Spatial regional planning in general and land use/land cover planning in particular are important tools to guide the sustainable urban and environment development. In areas of high population growth followed by high rate of increase in demand for providing facilities and utilities and secondly undergoing rapid land use change, there is an urgent need for information which is accurate, adequate and frequently updated.

This paper indicates the ability of Remote Sensing and GIS in capturing spatial-temporal data. Attempt was made to capture as accurate as possible land use/ land cover classes as they change through time. The system used to obtain such information must provide an inventory of land use and must be able to monitor changes in land use as a basis for predicting future trend.

Remote sensing, which has the most advanced method of data acquisition systems can provide accurate, timely, reliable and up to date urban spatial information at a regular interval. In the present study, multi date high resolution satellite data are used to obtain spatial information on Bhubaneswar City.

A digital database of study area for different period has been generated for which quantitative analysis and computer processing of spatial variables are possible. The systems are designed in such a way, inputting of photo/image derived data is found to be very easy and secondly simultaneous inputting of both map polygons and polygon identifier reduced the time in data inputting and storage. Selective retrieval of information or map units from the digital data base has been done easily when required during analysis.

In the present study only three times data (2000, 2005 and 2010) was analyzed for detailed study. It would be of immense use if sequential high resolution data of cities are taken at next five year interval to study the spatial structure, growth monitoring and population projection. The present trend of growth of the city is high in southwest and north direction in comparison to other directions for which the development activities in these directions requires monitoring at interval. The rate of development of informal activity is high inside and beyond the municipal boundary for which strict planning control is required in these areas to avoid haphazard growth and other planning problems. The above study provides a methodology for better estimation of urban growth and population using various land uses with time.

Geographical information system (GIS) and satellite images have been used in this study to provide spatial inputs and test the statistical model describing the growth. The model developed in this study can be used for predicting the future land uses even when not much of old land use data is available. This is useful for the urban planning authorities in developing countries where land use data is not available regularly. Besides this the encroachments on environmentally sensitive areas like river banks, forest, hill slopes can be detected and recorded on a routine basis using remote sensing and GIS, thus improving the ability of urban planners to respond to rapid urban changes and threats to the environment.

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